

EBRAINS 2.0

M6.4 HPC Container

Figure 1: The EBRAINS Software Distribution deployed to an HPC-optimized Container¹

(CC BY-SA 3.0 Container photograph by Wikipedia user KMJ)

¹ This is a symbolic image: High-Performance Computing (HPC) machine cabinets are visible in the background, the logo of the EBRAINS Software Distribution (ESD) logo is shown on the side of a standard ISO container representing the “containerization” of software deployments for HPC applications.

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Abstract:	<p>This milestone outlines the deployment of the EBRAINS Software Distribution (ESD) in High-Performance Computing (HPC) environments based on site-specific, optimized container images. We present our modularized build flow that leverages optimized low-level libraries —such as those for communication, numerical computation, or GPU acceleration— provided by system administrators at each site, ensuring that the EBRAINS software components are tuned for optimal performance. In addition, the deployment process is controlled by the common EBRAINS Continuous Integration (CI) system for automated build and testing, ensuring consistency, reproducibility and reliability. Designed for scalability, this system can be easily extended to new sites, facilitating widespread adoption of EBRAINS software in the future. A comprehensive performance evaluation demonstrates the effectiveness of the deployment strategy, highlighting its efficiency and potential for large-scale research applications.</p>		

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1. Introduction

1.1 Modern Scientific Software

Modern software that drives scientific research often relies on tool stacks from different communities, with quality ranging from professionally maintained to less actively supported. EBRAINS software tools span multiple disciplines, enabling data analysis, simulations, modelling, and complex data processing in different domains using different computational resources. To maximize quality and performance, they require expertise in the relevant scientific domain, programming or software engineering, and sometimes even computing-resource specific knowledge. Research Software Engineering (RSE) is an approach that emphasizes the sustainability of software throughout its lifecycle, from development to maintenance and optimization. This approach improves software quality, ensures reproducibility, and promotes long-term collaboration by ensuring availability, reliability, and robustness. While these aspects have not received much attention in some areas in the past², a strong community has emerged within EBRAINS that follows the principles of sustainable software development and deployment.

1.2 The EBRAINS Software Distribution (ESD)

Quoting the [announcement of the first ESD Hackathon](#), held in Heidelberg at the end of November 2024:

The aim of the [EBRAINS Software Distribution \(ESD\)](#)³ is to integrate [EBRAINS tools and workflow](#)⁴s in order to create a unified software ecosystem that facilitates the use, development, and deployment of scientific software for reproducible and scalable environments. The ESD has been designed for use in interactive and high-performance computing applications, and will soon facilitate service deployments. A container-packaged version will enable end users to leverage the EBRAINS ecosystem on their laptops, workstations, or their HPC system of choice.

To ensure a well-defined software environment at any point in time, the ESD is versioned and each version defines the set of contained software tools and their versions⁵. It follows a (roughly) 4-month release cycle. The current version (25.02) tracks 73 EBRAINS-related top-level tools and their approx. 800⁶ transient dependencies.

1.2.1 ESD — Continuous Integration

The ESD is developed in a [public git repository](#)⁷. The change management process follows a distributed development approach: developers can fork the repository, test and prepare their own changes before the ESD maintainers have to be involved. A code review process ensures quality control, while the automated CI system provides confidence in the validity of proposed changes. The following figure provides an overview of the development and deployment workflow:

² Hocquet, A., Wieber, F., Gramelsberger, G. et al. Software in science is ubiquitous yet overlooked. Nat Comput Sci 4, 465–468 (2024). DOI: [10.1038/s43588-024-00651-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s43588-024-00651-2)

³ <https://gitlab.ebrains.eu/ri/tech-hub/platform/esd/>

⁴ https://gitlab.ebrains.eu/ri/tech-hub/platform/esd/ebrains-spack-builds/-/tree/master/packages?ref_type=heads

⁵ This is similar to Linux distributions.

⁶ The exact number depends on the deployment target (e.g., 855 for the ebrains lab deployment).

⁷ <https://gitlab.ebrains.eu/ri/tech-hub/platform/esd>

See the [ESD's README.md⁸](#) and [ESD wiki⁹](#) for links to detailed descriptions. The latest addition to our development and deployment flow is the “ESD HPC container” (marked by an ellipse in blue).

1.3 High-performance Computing (HPC)

High-performance computing resources often encompass advanced, large-scale computing systems and technologies. Scientific users of such resources often perform complex calculations and handle large volumes of data. To use these systems efficiently, HPC-scalable scientific software codes and machine software libraries have to be used in conjunction. This machine-specific tuning makes building such software a non-trivial task.

1.4 “Containerization”

Packaging a software environment (incl. its dependencies) into a “standalone” unit¹⁰ is often called “Containerization”. In typical applications, the container is “lightweight” (i.e. minimum software environment required to perform a certain task) and portable between (similar) machines. This process is orthogonal to a structured software build flow, as described in the ESD section above. Combining a structured software build flow and containerization allows for portable deployments of the ESD.

⁸ <https://gitlab.ebrains.eu/ri/tech-hub/platform/esd/ebrains-spack-builds/-/blob/master/README.md>

⁹ <https://gitlab.ebrains.eu/ri/tech-hub/platform/esd/ebrains-spack-builds/-/wikis/home>

¹⁰ Typically, this is a image file that contains a filesystem or multiple filesystems, or even layers of changes of filesystems.

1.4.1 HPC Containerization

In the realm of HPC, machine-specific configuration makes it difficult to provide useful “standalone” container images. In particular, low-level libraries such as those needed for efficient data communication (MPI) or GPU acceleration (CUDA) often need to be aligned to the site-specific installation. Hence, the portability aspect of containerization is not universally valid in HPC. However, containerization can still provide significant benefits:

- Reproducibility
- Simplified CI and build testing
- (non-system-admin) Deployment
- Software start up performance

2. Methods

2.1 Linux Namespaces

The Linux operating system is ubiquitously used in contemporary High-Performance Computing. Modern versions¹¹ of the kernel provide support for the separation of “namespaces” (e.g., mount, pid, net, ipc, uts, user, cgroup, time) — environments that partition kernel resources such that individual processes see “their own” set of resources. In HPC, especially the “cgroup” namespace, is used for compute resource (CPU set/affinity, memory constraints) separation — however, for software deployment, providing a user-defined view of the filesystem, can be beneficial.

2.1.1 Apptainer/Singularity

Apptainer/Singularity is a container runtime that focuses on HPC applications. In contrast, other runtimes often focus on “cloud computing”-type applications —i.e. service encapsulation—, e.g., via docker, or application software deployment, e.g. via flatpak/snap. Apptainer/Singularity is widely supported on HPC sites, for details see the following table:

Table 1: Apptainer availability at EBRAINS and EuroHPC sites

Site	Apptainer/Singularity Version
JSC: JUSUF/JURECA/JUWELS/JEDI	Apptainer 1.3.6
CINECA: Leonardo	Singularity ≥3.8.7
CINECA: Galileo100	Singularity ≥3.8.0
CEA: Joliot-Curie	Support for converting from apptainer images
CSC: LUMI	SingularityCE
BSC: MareNostrum 5	SingularityCE ≥4.1.5

¹¹ Initial support appeared over twenty years ago; LXC has been providing containerization since 2008.

LXP: MeluXina	Apptainer $\geq 1.2.4$ Singularity $\geq 3.8.4$
Karolina	Apptainer
Vega	Singularity
Deucalion	Singularity $\geq 3.11.3$

In extreme cases, our investigation found that image building can be fully encapsulated in unprivileged userspace (via “proot” using `ptrace()` and `seccomp` functionality to reimplement syscalls in userspace).

2.1.2 Container Image

Some aspects of containerized software optimized for specific HPC sites are tightly bound to low-level system libraries such as MPI and CUDA. Furthermore, numerical libraries that are optimized by system experts for the machine specifics can often be found on HPC sites. Therefore, using a “transparent” base image for containerized software ecosystems can be beneficial. Lower-level software components (e.g. MPI, CUDA, but also BLAS, or other numerical, libraries) are transparently exposed into the container at build and runtime, while the container image itself does only contain the ESD deployment.

3. Results

3.1 Site-specific Configuration and “External Packages”

The spack-based definition of the ESD makes use of optimized system libraries as “external packages”, and the build process incorporates these packages as preinstalled components, i.e. the libraries are taken as installed, and no build is performed. By this, the spack-based installation of EBRAINS software packages makes use of performance-optimized software packages that are available on a specific system. However, this site-specific optimization often prevents the portability of the container to other systems (except in cases where Application Binary Interface (ABI) compatibility can be ensured— e.g., for some MPI libraries).

3.2 Automation and CI

To create HPC-optimized container images of the ESD, the build must (typically) occur on the same hardware architecture. This is achieved using a custom, access-restricted CI runner deployed on the HPC login node, which has access to site-specific optimized software libraries and the HPC resource manager. Within EBRAINS CI, we utilize this runner to dispatch builds of the ESD, specifically the HPC container image, onto the HPC system. The process begins by preparing the container build environment, ensuring necessary tools are available for tasks like spack operation, converting image types and uploading images to OCI container registries. Concurrently, all required software sources are downloaded. Next, the ESD build process begins within a container that uses a “transparent” base image, exposing the local HPC site’s software installation. Finally, a compressed filesystem image (the “container image”) is generated, containing the filesystem created during the container build.

3.2.1 Application Start up

Program startup performance on HPC systems can be significant due to the need to access network filesystems. In particular, interpreter languages like Python often perform extensive directory walks, resulting in numerous filesystem accesses that negatively affect startup times. Containerization helps to address this issue by packing most software components into a single read-only image file stored on the network filesystem. Once the image is accessed, the Linux operating system starts to cache the file, eliminating the need for subsequent costly POSIX filesystem accesses. This approach not only speeds up program start up but also reduces the overhead associated with repeated file access, leading to improved overall performance.

3.3 Validation

To validate the container-packaged EBRAINS software distribution (ESD), we ran typical HPC simulation packages from the ESD and specifically evaluated the performance of the *arbor multi-compartment neuron simulation library* utilizing GPU-based acceleration. The benchmarks were executed on the JUSUF HPC machine at JSC, allowing for a direct comparison between a previously validated machine installation and our new HPC container setup. This comparison helps ensure that the containerized environment delivers comparable or enhanced performance for complex simulations.

3.3.1 Benchmark: “arbor”¹²

Arbor is an open-source simulation library, designed for simulating large networks of morphologically detailed neurons. It is optimized for large-scale simulations on HPC clusters using distributed computing and GPU acceleration. These features make Arbor a good choice for initial scaling tests.

3.3.1.1 Validation of the HPC Container: Weak Scaling Runs using JUSUF at JSC

To validate the ESD deployment into an apptainer image, we compare the simulation and setup runtime of a dedicated arbor benchmark. We make use of JUSUF’s GPU partition (1x V100 per node, 16GiB of GPU memory, ≥32 nodes). All deployments used the same compiler, MPI and CUDA libraries and versions. For the arbor simulation engine we used the same build-time parameters¹³.

We compare the performance of three deployment styles:

- “Flat”: this is a classical HPC deployment that installs arbor on top of the site-provided software exposed as modules¹⁴.
- “Image”: This is the deployment style we describe in this document.
- “Spack”: This is a flat (i.e. non-containerized) deployment style that uses the spack build-from-source package manager to manage dependencies, and to build and install software.

The following plots show Benchmark Simulation setup and run times; each plot shows the timing results for the three deployment styles when sweeping over an increasing problem size distributed onto an increasing number of compute resources:

¹² Cumming, B. (2024) “Arbor v0.10.0”. Zenodo. doi: [10.5281/zenodo.13284789](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13284789).

¹³ ARB_WITH_ASSERTIONS=OFF ARB_WITH_MPI=ON ARB_WITH_PYTHON=OFF
ARB_VECTORIZE=ON ARB_GPU=cuda ARB_USE_GPU_RNG=OFF
CMAKE_CUDA_ARCHITECTURES=70

¹⁴ In JUSUF’s stage 2025 environment, we used GCC/13.3.0 ParaStationMPI/5.10.0-1 CUDA/12.

The results have been compared to previous benchmark runs and validated by the arbor team. With respect to measurement precision (approx. 3s for init, 0.5s for run times), all simulation run times are identical — i.e. the different deployment styles do not show any effect on runtime performance and reasonable weak scaling behaviour of arbor can be confirmed. The setup times for the flat deployment are significantly lower, which is an effect that the authors and the arbor team cannot explain at this point in time.

3.3.1.2 Additional Scaling Tests

To put the previous weak scaling runs into perspective, we evaluated the scaling performance of [Arbor¹⁵](#) using benchmarks conducted on the [JUWELS¹⁶](#) and [JUSUF¹⁷](#) supercomputing clusters at the Jülich Supercomputing Centre (JSC). The Arbor software was installed using the flat installation method as detailed on the [Arbor webpage¹⁸](#). The arbor EuroHPC [benchmarking suite¹⁹](#) consisted of three primary tests: stress testing²⁰ on a single node, weak scaling, and strong scaling²¹.

Single-Node Stress Test: On the JUWELS cluster, we simulated between 200 and 5,800 cells. The stress test showed a generally linear increase in simulation time as the number of cells increased, indicating that computational load scales predictably with problem size. However, some unexplained fluctuations were observed between 4000 to 5000 cells.

Weak scaling runs: We simulated systems on JUWELS where each node contained 1,300 cells (e.g. for 64 nodes, the total number of cells was 83,200). Weak scaling tests showed relatively stable simulation times as the number of nodes increased, though some fluctuations were present.

Strong scaling runs: Strong scaling tests, conducted on JUSUF and JUWELS with a fixed problem size of 128,000 cells, using 2, 4, 8, 16, 32 and 64 nodes. The results visualized in a log-log plot, demonstrated near-ideal linear scaling, indicating efficient resource utilization.

¹⁵ <https://arbor-sim.org/>

¹⁶ <https://www.fz-juelich.de/en/ias/jsc/systems/supercomputers/juwels>

¹⁷ <https://www.fz-juelich.de/en/ias/jsc/systems/supercomputers/jusuf>

¹⁸ https://docs.arbor-sim.org/en/latest/install/build_install.html

¹⁹ <https://github.com/thorstenhater/euhpc-arbor-benchmark>

²⁰ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Stress_testing_\(computing\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Stress_testing_(computing))

²¹ <https://hpc-wiki.info/hpc/Scaling>

3.3.1.3 Future work

The current work was carried out on JUWELS and JUSUF. In the next phase, we aim to extend this work to EuroHPC systems and to conduct benchmark runs of a representative set of HPC-related software tools included in the EBRAINS Software Distribution for flat, spack-based flat, and containerized installations. Another direction we are currently exploring is performing the same benchmarking on clusters with larger-scale GPU-accelerated machines JSC and CINECA²². Additionally, we are exploring the energy usage of running such benchmarks.

4. Discussion

The EBRAINS Software Distribution has evolved significantly over the past years. After the *first ESD Hackathon* in November 2024, a container-image-deployed version was commissioned, and we have since built upon these developments to create a site-specific HPC container image. This new containerized version leverages site-specific libraries—such as CUDA, MPI and BLAS libraries—while offering a simplified environment compared to traditional flat installations. Following up on benchmark integration efforts at the *EBRAINS Days 2025* (Internal & Developer Day) in Heidelberg, we have demonstrated on the JUSUF HPC machine that the containerized software deployment can achieve flat-install-equivalent runtime performance on HPC machines. We validated the chosen benchmark on JUWELS and JUSUF using a classical flat installation. Looking ahead, future steps will focus on extending the benchmark coverage to a representative set of HPC-relevant EBRAINS tools, and on exploring generically-optimized HPC images and assessing the potential performance impact of such optimizations.

²² <https://leonardo-supercomputer.cineca.eu/>